

Shifting the Light: Reframing Research Ethical Approval through Participatory Practice in Irish Higher Education

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Participatory Action Research (PAR) emphasises collaboration with people with lived experience. In academia, PAR studies must secure research approval from an ethics committee. Research ethics committees (RECs) are higher education institutional bodies responsible for reviewing research proposals to ensure they meet ethical and legal standards to protect research participants. RECs require researchers to complete a formal research ethics application (REA) to obtain approval before commencing a study. Current research ethics approval processes in Irish Higher Education Institutions (HEI), which are universities, colleges and institutes providing higher level education and research, often exclude community researchers at the REA stage. This exclusion raises critical questions about power, ownership, moral values, and knowledge creation. Principle-based ethics rooted in biomedical traditions are deeply embedded in the research world and prioritises protection and risk avoidance over inclusive practice, failing to support the relational, inclusive, and dynamic nature of PAR. REA is more than administrative paperwork ensuring ethical compliance; it is the foundation for research integrity. When community researchers are excluded from this foundation, the research process begins with inequality and exclusion. As a result, the ethical foundation for participatory research is weak. This study asks: *How can community researchers be included in South East Technological University's (SETU) research ethics application process?* Through critical reflection on practice and literature, this issue in practice leads to a challenge within existing frameworks; namely in considering who is protected, and who decides these ethical guidelines. If ethics frameworks are to uphold justice, they must evolve beyond compliance -based protectionism and instead enable shared ownership, respect, and inclusion from the outset. By reframing RECs not as gatekeepers, but as enablers of transformative, co-created knowledge, this study contributes to a broader movement for more inclusive, participatory, and socially just research ethics practices. It calls for empowering community researchers as equal partners from research origin to conclusion and challenges the academic community to rethink what constitutes ethical, inclusive research.

Keywords: Participatory Action Research, Ethical Approval, Inclusion, Power dynamics, Knowledge Co-creation, Ethical reform

Highlights

- Tensions between Participatory Action Research (PAR) and Research Ethics Committees (RECs) stem from bureaucratic, risk averse and principle-based ethics that often exclude community researchers from early research development and approval stages
- This exclusion creates power imbalances between the institution, academic and community researchers and limits inclusive knowledge production
- This Problem of Practice highlights the urgent need to rethink ethical frameworks and develop collaborative, inclusive protocols that better align with PAR values

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Introduction

Participatory action research (PAR) values the expertise of people with lived experience, yet in Irish Higher Education (HEI), ethical approval processes often exclude them. Community researchers are non-academic collaborators, with lived experience or expertise in a particular field. Community researchers typically join research projects *after* approval has been granted, raising key concerns about *power, ownership, moral values, and knowledge creation*.

A familiar story illustrates this misalignment; a man searches under a light for his lost keys. Asked where he lost them, he points to a dark area nearby and says, ‘I am looking here because the light is better’. This metaphor illustrates how institutional research ethics policies often focus on what is easily regulated, rather than on the real ethical complexities of PAR. The ‘light’ represents traditional ethical practices that hide the need to shift to a more inclusive and dynamic model to include community researchers from the initial research idea. Inclusive research is based on Freire’s (1970) contention that research is done ‘with’, rather than ‘to’ or on behalf of individuals, suggesting the need to rethink ethical approval processes to include community researchers from the start.

Without inclusion from the onset, participatory research risks becoming tokenistic. Current ethical procedures may unintentionally silence the very voices PAR claims to amplify. This study asks: **How could community researchers be included in SETU’s research ethics application process?** This article explores how institutional ethical procedures could evolve to include community researchers within the approval process. The following sections draw on researcher positionality, literature, and institutional practice to explore a more inclusive model of ethical review.

A Problem of Practice in Participatory Research

Drawing on my experience as a Technological University (TU) lecturer and PAR researcher, this section examines how current research ethics committees (RECs) policies conflict with the collaborative and inclusive values of participatory research. My Problem of Practice stems from lived experience and a real-world dilemma (Ma *et al.* 2018). In navigating academic and health RECs, I have observed that my institution's policies and

procedures exclude community researchers from the research ethics application stage (REA). This exclusion creates knowledge creation imbalances, as RECs approved research questions often lack input from individuals and communities. Consequently, academic researchers may bear the emotional and moral burden of conducting research that does not fully reflect individual or community perspectives.

PAR is defined as ‘a collaborative effort in which people whose lives are affected by issues being researched are partners in designing, undertaking, and disseminating research to influence socially just change’ (Banks and Byrdon Miller, 2019, p.3). Its principles are centred on Freire’s Pedagogy of the Oppressed (2005) and Fals-Borda’s Action Research Theory (1991), both of which value lived experience. The core principles of PAR are epistemic justice, which is the valuing of different sources of knowledge, inclusion and moral accountability to individuals and communities (Banks and Brydon Miller, 2019). PAR calls for meaningful inclusion of community researchers at all stages of the research process, from posing research questions to dissemination of research findings. To unpack this further, a deeper exploration of researcher positionality and how it shaped my problem of practice is required.

Researcher Positionality

Reflecting on my positionality is central to understanding how I developed this problem of practice. Cooper *et al.* (2024) define positionality as how worldview, social identity, and socio-political context shape perceptions and research. My social care qualification and professional roles in the Health Service Executive, Ireland’s national body for overseeing public health and social care, have shaped my understanding of knowledge, practice and human agency. Roles in policy development, drug education, addiction service management and lecturing further inform my professional perspective. These experiences create a positive bias toward PAR, reinforced by literature calling for RECs to facilitate inclusion rather than act as gatekeepers or barriers to inclusive research (O’Neill *et al.* 2022). These positional influences heighten my awareness of systemic tensions that exist between PAR researchers and RECs.

Gaps in Existing Ethical Frameworks in Participatory Research

Tensions between PAR and RECs

The relationship between PAR researchers and RECs is not always harmonious. It is no secret that qualitative researchers at times see RECs as the enemy and have a ‘chorus of complaints’ and PAR researchers echo many of these concerns (Bell *et al.* 2020, p. 537). PAR researchers accuse RECs of being overly bureaucratic (Huysamen and Sanders, 2021) and overstepping their reach and regulatory powers (Haggerty, 2004; 2016). The bureaucratic and risk-averse nature of RECs leads to research approval delays (Webber and Brunger, 2018) or imposing embargoes on releasing sensitive topic research (Kindynis and Fleetwood, 2024). Another consequence of risk aversion is the institutions' power to constrain and control community researchers' involvement in research. There remains limited literature on how risk aversion practices specifically impact the role and autonomy of community researchers.

In many cases, RECs challenge research questions and methodological decision-making based on moral and cultural judgements (Burdalaze *et al.* 2024). Some commentators argue that these moral and cultural values overemphasise participant risk and harm to the exclusion of academic researcher harm (Keene, 2022). RECs moral and cultural values reflect Kant's principle-based ethics, particularly the ‘do no harm’ principle (Doyle and Buckley, 2017). RECs moral and cultural judgements singularly focus on protecting vulnerable individuals from research and researcher risk and harm (Bracken-Roche *et al.* 2017). This protection starts at the REA stage by assuming that collaborating with community researchers before ethical approval is a potential source of harm. The lack of discussion on this presumption in academic literature points to a need to critically rethink moral frameworks that guide the ethical review process.

The impact of principle-based ethics on knowledge production

Paphitis (2018, p.364) suggests that research practices within academic institutions can enable academic researchers to ‘subtly and not so subtly ignore and discredit ways of knowing and understanding the world’ from non-privileged individuals and groups. This reflects how institutional power operates through control of legitimate knowledge creation, aligning with Foucault's concept that discourse is the ‘conjunction of power and knowledge’ (Kenway, 1990, p. 128). This critique is echoed in

international literature (e.g. Tamariz *et al.* 2015; Stephenson *et al.* 2020; Nind *et al.* 2013; Oye *et al.* 2019; Wilson *et al.*, 2018; Doyle and Buckley, 2017, p. 96) which claims that principle-based ethical frameworks often silence alternative knowledge production in qualitative research. Such researchers argue that principle-based ethics often create significant problems for qualitative research which can be subjective, messy, and non-linear. The sustained resistance to reforming these frameworks reflects institutional power and reinforces community researchers' lack of authority and power to challenge established norms (Wilson, 2018, p. 194). Using principle-based measures to control knowledge production locates research ownership with the institution and academic. Little attention is given to the exclusionary practices of omitting community researchers from generating research questions or designing research projects.

Unresolved ethical challenges in PAR

This literature identifies several unresolved ethical challenges in PAR research; for example, power dynamics, researcher-participant relationships, and ownership (Burduladze *et al.* 2024; Duggan, 2021; Facer and Enright, 2016). Despite improvements in RECs practices and procedures, PAR highlight the need for a review of RECs ethical procedures to support community researchers' engagement (Cross *et al.* 2015). Noorani *et al.* (2017) argue that medicalised frameworks used in ethical policies fail to accommodate diverse research methodologies and community researchers. McDonald and Capous-Desyllas (2021, p.364) call for RECs to 'create a new participant-researcher category and protocols to support community researchers'. These studies are concerned with research data collection, analysis and dissemination. However, they tend to overlook the ethical complexities that require further examination at pre-approval stage. One significant gap remains, the specific exclusion of community researchers from HEI REA process has received little attention. This omission has implications for ownership, power, moral values and epistemic justice in PAR.

Challenges like co-authorship (Miles, Renedo, and Marston, 2022), accountability (West and Schill, 2022), and gatekeeping (Irvine, 2012) further expose gaps in current policies. Additionally, "ethics creep" which extends RECs regulatory power, reinforces the need for ethics frameworks that align with participatory research's inclusive goals (Haggerty, 2004). Finally, Huysamen and Sanders highlight the inconsistent and the ad

hoc nature of RECs decisions, noting that reviewers often rely ‘on their own discretion and intuition’ (2021, p. 954). Although well documented in the literature post approval, these concerns remain underexplored at pre-approval stage.

The undervalued role of community researchers

Despite these calls for reform, research approval practices, procedures or policies receive little attention in academic, health or community participatory research literature. Academic articles often assume ethical approval was granted by an institutional RECs and was written by an academic. In contrast, health or community studies imply community researchers' involvement in the REA stage. However, descriptions of how this collaboration occurred are rarely documented. Opsal *et al.* (2016, p.1148) recommended that American Institutional Research Boards create opportunities for researchers and participants to ‘have meaningful dialogue with committees before, during and after the research process’. While valuable, their recommendation does not address the lack of inclusion in the ethical review process. This raises an important question about the extent to which REA in health and community research are developed collaboratively with community researchers, and whether consistent, inclusive protocols exist across institutions. This gap points to an opportunity; to develop an inclusive framework for REA processes and practices that includes ownership, power sharing, inclusive research framing, accountability, social and relational dynamics and epistemic justice. To fully understand these tensions, it is important to discuss how contemporary HEI ethical policies and practices evolved from principle-based biomedical traditions that may not align with PAR principles.

Problematising the Status Quo

Principle-based ethics and its influence on research governance

Principle-based ethical frameworks rooted in medical research continue to dominate research governance in higher education, despite their limitations in PAR contexts (Haggerty, 2016). Foundational documents, such as the Nuremburg Code (1949), Declaration of Helsinki (1964), and Belmont Report (1979) underpin much of contemporary research ethics. Rooted in Kantian ideas, these principle-based frameworks stress universal respect for persons and a duty to avoid harm. Kant’s key

principle that ‘each person should be respected as a unique individual, treated with dignity, and never used as a means to an end’ continues to inform ethical review processes (Banks and Brydon-Miller, 2019, p.11). While originally designed for medical research, they now dominate research in education, community, and statutory settings (Oye *et al.* 2019).

However, these policies are not immune to critique. As Bell (2006) argues once elevated to universal norms, policies like the Declaration of Helsinki become difficult to challenge even in the face of evolving ethical demands from more inclusive research approaches. Oye *et al.* (2019, p.1227) claim that there is ‘a need to revisit ethical research guidelines formulated in the Declaration of Helsinki, when it comes to research guidelines of informed consent, anonymity and integrity of research’. In practice, RECs when faced with perceived risks tend to adopt a default position of risk aversion to protect individuals from potential harm, which is a response to historical research abuses and misconduct. The Nazi experiments during World War 2 (Mitscherlich and Mielke 1949), the Tuskegee experiment (Reverby, 2000), and the tearoom experiments (Humphreys, 1975) are examples of devastating research misconduct.

PAR literature highlights further limitations of principle-based ethics; for example, ignoring additional ethical concerns such as ongoing consent (Doyle and Buckley, 2017). Principle-based ethical frameworks require consent as a standard once-off formality. In PAR, consent is situational, relational, and emerging and requires the academic researcher to be aware of changing consent needs (Oye *et al.* 2016). Academic researchers must rely on their moral beliefs when responding to individual situations, pausing to reflect on emotions, moods, and interactions. This includes regularly checking if community researchers are happy with their role and contribution. Relational ethics moves beyond paperwork and the ethical approval status to the real relationships between researchers and community researchers (Pei Jung *et al.* 2025). Academic researchers are required to identify ethical issues/concerns in advance of commencing research. However, PAR highlights emerging ethical issues during data collection or analysis (Tamariz *et al.* 2015). When community researchers are excluded from the REA stage, their insights into potential harms and risks are overlooked, and opportunities to connect research participants with relevant support or services may be lost. PAR literature

repeatedly asks RECs to include specific PAR ethical issues in ethical forms, policies, and procedures (Oye *et al.* 2019). Despite this, PAR ethical issues remain unaddressed, suggesting that RECs may be uncertain how to navigate these complexities and are hesitant to extend RECs policies and procedures to explore emerging PAR social and relational ethical issues.

Ironically, RECs are quick to remedy any perceived ethical risks based on moral and cultural values by changing a PAR research question, method, or sample group. These moral and cultural judgements singularly focus on protecting vulnerable individuals from research and researcher risk and harm (Bracken-Roche *et al.* 2017). Moral and cultural judgements frame research practices, research question framing, and ethical approval decisions (Keene, 2022). Drawing on Foucault's (1991) concept that knowledge is power, the tools of knowledge production, gatekeeping and dissemination maintain power within academia (Kaloscai, 2023). This section highlights ethical tensions experienced by PAR academics committed to participatory methods. These tensions stem from their dual commitment to complying with institutional governance while advocating for a more inclusive, relational, and reflexive approach to ethical processes.

Participatory Action Research Values and Principles in Research Practice

Academic privilege and unequal partnerships

HEI principle-based ethical frameworks and academic authority can unintentionally undermine the principles of PAR, particularly when it comes to REA processes. From my experience, the role and privileged position of HEI academic researchers, often middle class, highly educated, and institutionally empowered, can unintentionally contradict participatory research principles (De Backer, 2022, p.722). Academic researchers are in a position of privilege because of their social power relations within the research community. Privileged positions stem from the researcher's professional role, research access, knowledge, and 'social situations shape our interactions with evidence, belief, and knowledge (de Saint-Croix, 2020, p. 419). The act of writing the REA positions the academic as the lead authority, setting the tone for an

unequal partnership. The application is written on behalf of community researchers, limiting their agency to shape the research from the start.

PAR academic researchers act as a bridge between the HEI RECs, community researchers, research participants, funders, and stakeholders (Peterson, 2020). They hold many roles, sometimes simultaneously, for example as a RECs member, researcher, participant, grant/funder authors. PAR academic researchers must reconcile the competing roles and responsibilities of the institution and PAR principles. These competing roles can strain collaboration, particularly when institutional power undermines epistemic justice.

Epistemic injustice and the marginalisation of community researchers

Paphitis (2018, p. 363) explains epistemic justice as ‘whose knowledge counts’, a critical concern of PAR. Duggan (2021) claims that PAR is misused by academia, extracting knowledge and perspectives from community researchers with the rewards tipped in favour of the academic. For example, the academic receives credit for the research idea, and their name is first in the author list. Academics’ status is further reinforced by their authority to generate research questions, decide research priorities and apply for HEI research approval before collaborating with community researchers.

While academics operate from a position of epistemic and institutional privilege, this contrasts with the more constrained and controlled role of community researchers. They are often invited into the research process after RECs approval. This sequencing limits community researchers' input in research framing and unintentionally reinforces the institutional hierarchy that PAR aims to dismantle. For example, the SETU policy states that all researchers should ‘obtain approval from the relevant authority, the SETU REC or school ***prior to commencing any research activities***’ (SETU, 2023, p.18). As a result, academics independently draft REA, excluding community researchers from shaping the research question, methodology and design. This shifts power to the academic to lead and control the direction of the study.

This exclusion is not merely procedural; it has broader epistemological and ethical implications for how knowledge is produced in participatory contexts (Fricker, 2007). Once approved by the RECs, the blueprint for the research reflects the academics perspective, limiting opportunities for community input at design stage (Groot *et al.*

2022). Academics are required to carry out the research project as per ethical approval, which can constrain flexibility once the study begins. This approach can contradict the ethos of PAR as it risks silencing community researcher voices from highlighting research areas that matter to their daily lives (Kaloscai, 2023). It may also restrict academics from collaborating with individuals/communities to co-create research questions or investigate problems of practice. Community researchers may participate in a predesigned project rather than shaping the research. Such practices risk undervaluing the role and expertise of community researchers in leading knowledge creation.

Personal reflection on procedural exclusion and its ethical consequences

These institutional procedures have posed concrete ethical and relational challenges in my own work. I encountered this disconnect when reconciling different processes for the same research study and group of community researchers. In one REA (HSE) community researchers were actively involved in the process, whereas my institutions policy excluded them. This raised important questions for me; what, if any, impact does community researchers' involvement in REA have on the research outcomes and integrity? What are the consequences of exclusion at REA stage on research question development and knowledge creation? What, if any, are the consequences of exclusion on social and relational outcomes between academic, community researchers and HEI?

These tensions challenged me as a researcher and raised concerns about tokenism in PAR. I was uncomfortable silencing voices and perspectives at the REA stage and struggled navigating different RECs research practices with the same group of community researchers (Ni She *et al.* 2019). This personal experience echoes concerns raised in literature. Fiscella *et al.* (2015) suggest the integration of Institutional Research Boards and clinical ethical committees to increase support for broader stakeholder engagement and provide consistent practices across ethical committees. Further literature documents how multi-site ethical practices and procedures are inconsistent, causing delays and creating relational and procedural tensions (Trace and Kolstoe, 2017; Oye *et al.* 2019). The challenges for academic researchers applying to multiple RECs for ethical approval are well documented (Stephenson *et al.* 2020). I have faced similar difficulties such as delays and emerging ethical challenges such as relationship tensions, power relations, and decision-making associated with inconsistent feedback from RECS (Bassu

et al. 2021). These practice complexities cast a spotlight on deeper questions about authority and control within ethical review processes.

A New Light: My Research Lens

This study challenges the current ethics frameworks by questioning not only who is protected but who gets to decide the rules. If ethics frameworks are to uphold justice, they must evolve beyond protectionism and become tools for inclusion, respect, and shared ownership for developing research ideas. This research contributes to a future where RECs ethical processes are not gatekeepers but enablers of transformative, co-created knowledge. Thus, empowering community researchers as essential co-creators of knowledge from research origin to dissemination.

Limitations

This section outlines ethical and political considerations focusing solely on researcher positionality. This does not diminish the importance of methodology, consent, privacy, risk to participants, or institutional resistance to ethical reforms. Academics hold a privileged position in PAR (De Backer, 2022). My positionality can shape all elements of this proposed study. This includes decisions on research methodology and design, setting questions, and influencing how findings are presented and analysed. For me as a privileged insider researcher, reflexivity is crucial to keeping my positionality in check.

Conclusion

This issue sits within the broader debates about reforming research ethics, changing who decides what counts as knowledge, and making academia more inclusive. While PAR is widely recognised for empowering communities and generating socially relevant knowledge, current ethics frameworks shaped by biomedical tradition struggle to support its principles. RECs often focus on risk avoidance and compliance, shining their light where it is easiest to see. This problem of practice is illuminating the shadows, shining a spotlight on the exclusion of community researchers from the research ethic approval stage. If research begins with exclusion, how can the rest of the research process be inclusive?

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